

**Reactive species and mechanisms of perfluorooctanoic acid
(PFOA) degradation in water by cold plasma: The role of
HV waveform, reactor design, water matrix and plasma gas**

by

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Abstract

The scope of this study was to optimize dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) plasma for the degradation of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) in water by comparing several critical aspects such as pulsed-plasma waveform (nanosecond and microsecond high-voltage (HV) pulses), reactor configuration (gas-liquid treatment and underwater plasma bubbles), water matrix and plasma gas. The physicochemical properties and species concentration of plasma-treated water, under the aforementioned conditions, were also determined and correlated with PFOA degradation. PFOA was more efficiently degraded by air-liquid DBD compared to DBD-based underwater air-plasma bubbles consistent with the surfactant nature of PFOA and the more intense plasma-liquid interaction and species formation prevailing during gas-liquid treatment compared to plasma bubbles treatment. After 30 min of treatment, the degradation of PFOA in ultrapure water was >99.9%, 98.8, 95.1 and 63% under air-, N₂- Ar- and O₂-plasma respectively, whereas its degradation was almost equally effective in the whole range of its initial concentration (10 to 0.1 mg/L). Air was almost equally effective at degrading PFOA in ultrapure and tap water, while argon was much more effective at degrading PFOA in tap water (>99.9% after 20 min) possibly due to the prevailing alkaline conditions (pH ~8.7) favoring its degradation. Faster PFOA degradation was achieved under HV micropulses compared to HV nanopulses. Nevertheless, in terms of energy requirements, HV nanopulses were superior to HV micropulses, with the lowest electrical energy per order achieved under nanopulsed-argon (~23.6 kWh/m³). The results of this study could contribute important knowledge to the development of plasma-based treatment of PFOA-contaminated water.

Keywords: Cold plasma; Dielectric barrier discharge; Underwater plasma bubbles, PFOA, Water treatment; Nanosecond pulses.

1. Introduction

In the last decade, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) have become a main constituent of the persistent organic pollutants (POPs) list of the Stockholm Convention. Known as “forever chemicals” because of their remarkable persistency and ability to undergo long-range transport, they can move through soil to contaminate drinking water and accumulate to humans and animals [1-3]. There is a large number of publications in the last 30 years that verifies the existence of these chemicals in various environmental compartments, such as surface water, drinking water, rain water, and groundwater [4-6]. Thus, it has raised an increasing concern related to the control of the presence of these chemicals in environmental systems. PFASs consist of a fluorinated alkyl chain and a polar head group that give them surfactant-like properties, which makes them resilient and difficult to degrade effectively. Breaking a carbon-fluorine (C-F) bond is generally considered challenging because this bond is one of the strongest bonds in organic chemistry due to the high electronegativity of fluorine.

The removal of PFAS has been pursued by different methods mainly physical, chemical, and biological treatment. Several adsorption methods have been developed to remove PFAS from water, including granular activated carbon (GAC), ion exchange (IX), and polymers [7-10]. These methods seem to be promising in effectively removing some of these compounds but lead to the generation of PFAS contaminated residues and concentrates. On the other hand, traditional biological degradation and advanced oxidation processes (e.g. ozonation, UV irradiation, UV-H₂O₂) which are dedicated to organic compounds mineralization have been proven to be unable to decompose PFAS effectively due to the multiple stable C-F bonds in the perfluoroalkyl moiety. Other oxidation methods, such as sonolytical processes, electrochemical oxidation, photocatalytic decomposition, and persulfate oxidation [11-14] require high

dosages of chemical reagents or expensive materials, are energy-consuming and sometimes secondary pollution (e.g. generation of perchlorate) needs to be addressed. Thus, it is essential to develop eco-innovative, cost- and energy-efficient technologies with minimal environmental impacts for the complete destruction of PFAS from multi-source wastewater based on the careful exploration of their destruction mechanisms.

Non-thermal plasma (NTP) has been established as a highly effective, rapid and energy efficient water remediation method [15-19]. NTP is considered an advantageous wastewater treatment technology that benefits from the tuned plasma chemistry and the simultaneous action of oxidative and reductive species, space charge and UV radiation. During plasma, numerous highly energetic processes trigger the generation of short-lived (e.g. $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\cdot\text{O}$, $\cdot\text{NO}$, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, e_{aq}^- , e^-) and long-lived (e.g. O_3 , H_2O_2 , NO_3^- , NO_2^-) reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) capable of directly activating the degradation process. The most commonly used plasma configurations include dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) and corona discharge reactors, which are based on the generation of plasma species in the gas phase and their subsequent diffusion in the liquid (gas-liquid treatment) [19-24].

An increasing number of studies is, recently, reported related to the treatment of PFAS destruction by non-thermal plasma. Gas-liquid plasma treatment seems to be effective since PFAS are peculiar class of pollutants exhibiting surfactant properties with a tendency to exist in the surface of water [25-27]. However, underwater plasma bubbles are, recently, proposed as an advantageous way to degrade organic pollutants (e.g. dyes, antibiotics) attributed to the effective and rapid diffusion of plasma species in water [28-30]. Thus, a comparison between gas-liquid plasma and underwater plasma bubbles for PFAS degradation is missing. Furthermore, despite the fact that the energy requirements of NTP are very promising, it is crucial to decrease the electrical energy

per order (E_{EO}) values by carefully choosing the most efficient solution, in terms of plasma source and plasma-liquid interaction, according to the target PFAS molecule to be removed [31].

Therefore, the reactor configuration/conditions, the high voltage (HV) waveform used to energize the plasma reactors, and the physicochemical water properties that maximize the production of plasma species and their interaction with the PFAS should be thoroughly investigated. This work is the first report comparing (i) gas-liquid DBD with DBD-based underwater plasma bubbles and (ii) HV microsecond pulses with HV nanosecond pulses for the degradation of PFOA in water by plasma. In addition to the effect of plasma configuration and plasma waveform, the influence of plasma gas and water matrix on the physicochemical properties of the plasma-treated water and the formation of plasma species was investigated in detail with the ultimate aim of correlating all these parameters with PFOA degradation and process energy requirements.

2. Experimental section

2.1 Materials and chemicals

PFOA ($C_8HF_{15}O_2$, $M= 414.07$ g/mol, purity 95%) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. For the preparation of PFOA solutions ultrapure water (UPW), obtained by the purification of deionized water with a Millipore system, or tap water (TW) were used. Dry air, nitrogen (N_2), argon (Ar) and oxygen (O_2) were supplied by Linde (Athens, Greece). Mass labeled PFAAs standard (MPFAC-24ES, Lot: PFAC24ES0221, Extraction Standard; 1.2 mL, 1000 ng/mL, Methanol) and Native PFAAs/Recovery standard (PFAC-24PAR, Lot: PFAC24PAR0321, Standard; 2 mL, 2000 ng/mL Methanol) were acquired from Wellington Laboratories (Ontario, Canada).

2.2. *Experimental set up and treatment conditions*

The experimental setup for the plasma generation and characterization is shown schematically in Fig. 1. It consisted of the plasma reactor, a HV power supply, a discharge (optical and electrical) characterization arrangement and a feeding gas system. Two different high voltage (HV) power supplies were used for the generation of plasma; either a microsecond pulsed- μ sp (Leap 100, PlasmaLeap Technologies) or a nanosecond pulsed HV generator-nsp (NPG-18/3500). In terms of discharge characterization, optical emission spectroscopy (AvaSpec-ULS2048CL-EVO, Avantes) was employed to investigate the major plasma reactive species produced in the gas phase during the discharge formation. The applied high voltage and the generated DBD current were recorded by means of a voltage probe (Tektronix P6015A) and current transformer (Pearson electronics 2877), respectively, on a digital oscilloscope (Rigol MSO2302A).

To explore the effect of the reactor geometry, two different plasma reactors were examined; a plane-to-plane gas-liquid dielectric barrier discharge (GLDBD) reactor and a DBD-based underwater plasma microbubbles (PMB) column, where the discharges are generated above and in the aqueous phase, in each case respectively (Fig. S1). The gas-liquid DBD reactor was a quartz reaction tank (55 mm inner diameter, 2 mm bottom thickness) with a stainless-steel disc (37 mm diameter) as the high voltage electrode and a second stainless-disc (70 mm diameter) as the grounded electrode. The high voltage electrode was inserted into a quartz dielectric (50 mm diameter, 2 mm thickness), when the grounded electrode was attached on the top of a hollow PTFE holder. The gap between the electrodes was fixed at about 10 mm, whereas the gap between the quartz dielectric surface and the aqueous solution surface was 2 mm. The

working gas was injected into the reaction tank and diffused over the water surface at a constant flow rate.

On the other hand, the design of the underwater plasma microbubble column is based on a coaxial DBD configuration (Fig. S1). It consisted of an inner quartz tube (5 mm inner diameter, 8 mm outer diameter) with a tightly inserted stainless-steel rod (4 mm diameter) acting as the high voltage electrode, and an outer quartz tube (12 mm inner diameter) at the base of which 10 holes were uniformly distributed. The plasma gas was introduced in the interspace between the two dielectric tubes and then diffused through the holes into the PFOA contaminated solution in the form of underwater plasma bubbles. The solution was placed in a cylindrical quartz vessel where in its external surface a stainless-steel grid was attached playing the role of the grounded electrode.

In the experiments, 15 mL and 70 mL of PFOA solution was treated in the GLDBD and PMB reactor, respectively. For microsecond-pulsed system, the treatment time of the experiments varied from 5 to 30 min whereas for nanosecond-pulsed system from 5 to 60 min. Various plasma working gases (air, nitrogen, argon, oxygen), initial pollutant concentrations (0.1, 1, 10 mg/L) and water matrices (ultrapure and tap water) were examined towards the degradation efficiency. Based on preliminary experiments and previous experience [30], the gas flow rate was fixed at 1.0 L/min for gas-liquid DBD whereas the corresponding one for PMB was 3.0 L/min. Nanopulsed experiments were performed under constant pulse voltage of 27.6 kV and pulse frequency of 200 Hz, while for micropulsed-plasma the corresponding values were 20.0 kV and 1000 Hz.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the experimental setup used to treat PFOA polluted water samples by cold plasma and (b) optical emission spectrum of air- and argon-plasma in the gas-liquid interface of the gas-liquid DBD reactor (HV waveform: micropulses).

2.3 *Reactive species identification and basic physicochemical characterization of plasma treated water*

The concentration of nitrate ions (NO_3^-) and nitrite ions (NO_2^-) was measured with QUANTOFIX® Relax unit (Macherey-Nagel, GmbH), using the corresponding test strips provided by the supplier. The concentration of O_3 was quantified with Hanna multi parameter photometer (HI83399-2) using appropriate reagents. For the determination of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) concentration, the titanium sulfate method was used. In this case, after the plasma treatment of a sample, a solution of titanium oxysulfate (TiSO_4) in 2 M sulfuric acid was added in the examined solution and then the absorbance at 407 nm was monitored in the UV-vis spectrum (Shimadzu UV-1900). OH radicals were detected using photoluminescence spectroscopy and terephthalic acid (TA) as trapping reagent [32]. pH and conductivity were recorded evaluating the physicochemical behavior of the solutions. The pH was measured through QUANTOFIX® Relax unit (Macherey-Nagel, GmbH) using calibrated QUANTOFIX test strips. The conductivity was measured using a multiparameter benchtop meter (Consort C1020) and the electrode (SK10T). The initial pH and conductivity of ultrapure water were 6.2 and 5 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively, while the corresponding ones of tap water were 6.8 and 507 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

2.4 *Electrical measurements and effectiveness parameters of the system*

The pulse energy (E_p) delivered to the reactor was calculated as the average of five successive measurements by integrating the instantaneous power $P(t)$ over the pulse duration (Eq. 1).

$$E_p = \int_{pulse} P(t)dt = \int_{pulse} V(t)I(t)dt \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where the $P(t)$ was estimated by the product of time varying voltage $V(t)$ and current $I(t)$, as received from the oscilloscope. The mean discharge power was calculated by multiplying the pulse frequency by the average pulse energy (Eq. 2).

$$P = fE_p \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

The degradation efficiency $D(\%)$, was calculated by the Eq. 3:

$$D(\%) = \left[\frac{C_0 - C_f}{C_0} \right] \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where C_0 and C_f are the PFOA concentration in water before and after plasma treatment.

For the determination of the pollutant degradation rate, the experimental data were fitted to a pseudo-first order equation (Eq. 4):

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_0}{C_f} \right) = kt \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

where k is the kinetic constant and t denotes the treatment time.

Energy yield (Y ; mg/kWh), which is defined as the amount of pollutant degraded per discharge power consumed, was calculated by the Eq. 5.

$$Y = \frac{C_0 V D}{Pt} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

Apart from energy yield, the electrical energy per order (E_{E0}) is another parameter which is used to describe the energy effectiveness of the plasma treatment and is defined as the electrical energy in kWh required to degrade a contaminant by one order of magnitude in 1 m³ of contaminated water. It was calculated by Eq. 6:

$$E_{E0} = \frac{Pt}{V \log \left(\frac{C_0}{C_f} \right)} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Where P is the power delivered to the reactor, V is the volume of treated solution, and t denotes the plasma treatment time.

2.5 *Chemical analysis of plasma treated PFOA samples*

Samples were analyzed by HPLC-MS/MS (Agilent 1260 Infinity II, Fig. S3) equipped with an Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 column (3.0 mm × 5 mm, 1.8 μm). Detection was performed at negative electrospray ionization (ESI) mode, and dynamic multiple-reaction monitoring mode (dMRM) was selected for target quantitative acquisition. The operation modes were developed based on Wellington method (the acquisition method attached with PFAAs standards) for samples with solvents mainly consisting of water. The mobile phase gradient for HPLC and the determination parameters of QQQ MS are deposited in Tables S1 and S2, respectively. Likewise, Qualitative Analysis of MassHunter acquisition data and MassHunter Quantitative for QQQ were employed for quantitative and qualitative analysis, respectively. Seven levels of calibration samples (0.5, 1, 5, 10, 25, 50, 100, unit: ng/mL) were prepared for calibration and quantitative analysis. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was 0.5 ng/mL, and the upper limit was 100 ng/mL. Two blank and quality control (QC) samples were added for every six to ten samples for quality control.

3. **Results and Discussion**

3.1 *Discharge characteristics of gas-liquid DBD and underwater plasma microbubbles reactors energized by HV microsecond and/or nanosecond pulses*

The pulse voltage, current and instantaneous power waveforms recorded during PFOA destruction by micropulsed- nanopulsed-plasma are shown in Fig. 2a and 2b, respectively. When the plasma reactor was energized by HV microsecond pulses, the measured peak current was ~0.4 A, resulting in an instantaneous power of ~8 kW (Fig. 2a). In contrast, under HV nanosecond pulses, the applied voltage was a unipolar positive pulse, while the current was bipolar consisting of the conduction and the

displacement current. The measured maximum amplitude of the nanopulse current was ~50 A resulting in an enormously high instantaneous power of ~1300 kW (Fig. 2b), which is ~160 times higher compared to that of micropulsed-plasma. Therefore, both the pulse current and the instantaneous power were ~2 orders of magnitude higher for the nanopulsed-plasma indicating the different mechanisms between the generation of nanosecond and microsecond pulsed discharges. However, due to the much lower duration of the nanosecond pulses, the average power dissipated in the plasma reactor was much lower for the nanopulsed-plasma (Table 1). Under air atmosphere, the calculated mean power of nanopulsed-DBD was ~1.1 W, while the corresponding one of micropulsed-DBD was ~60 W. Furthermore, for both HV waveforms, the mean power was lower under argon-plasma compared to air-plasma. In particular, under argon atmosphere, the micropulsed-DBD power decreased to 40.1 W (from 60 W in air-plasma), while the nanopulsed-DBD power decreased to 0.8 W (from 1.1 W in air-plasma) due to the lower breakdown voltage of argon-plasma compared to that of air-plasma. Finally, in accordance with previously published results on nanopulsed-plasma treatment [30], the mean power was lower for micropulsed-PMB (36.9 W) compared to micropulsed gas-liquid DBD (60 W) at a given applied voltage (20 kV) and plasma gas (air) despite the fact that the water volume was higher inside the PMB reactor.

Figure 2. Instantaneous voltage, current and power waveforms of the (a) micropulsed gas-liquid DBD and (b) nanopulsed gas-liquid DBD reactor during PFOA treatment (nanopulse voltage: 27.6 kV; nanopulse frequency: 200 Hz; micropulse voltage: 20.0 kV; micropulse frequency: 1000 Hz).

Table 1. Average power dissipated in the plasma reactors under the various experimental conditions.

Plasma reactor	HV waveform, pulse voltage (kV)/frequency (Hz)	Plasma gas	Power (W)
DBD-based underwater plasma microbubbles	Micropulses, 20.0 kV/1000 Hz	Air	36.9
Gas-liquid DBD	Micropulses, 20.0 kV/1000 Hz	Air	60.0
Gas-liquid DBD	Micropulses, 20.0 kV/1000 Hz	Argon	40.1
Gas-liquid DBD	Nanopulses, 27.6 kV/200 Hz	Air	1.1
Gas-liquid DBD	Nanopulses, 27.6 kV/200 Hz	Argon	0.8

3.2 *Effect of reactor geometry, plasma gas and water matrix on plasma species and physicochemical water properties*

3.2.1 *Identification of plasma excited species in the gas phase*

Optical emission spectroscopy was conducted for both gas-liquid and underwater plasma microbubbles reactors to detect the main excited molecular and atomic plasma species under air and argon atmospheres (Fig. 1b and Fig. S1c, respectively). The OES spectrum in the gas-liquid DDB was recorded targeting the gas-liquid interface, while the corresponding one in the plasma bubbles reactor was recorded targeting the bubble-liquid interface. Similar OES spectra were recorded between the two reactors. In particular, under air-plasma, the spectrum is dominated by excited nitrogen molecules (N_2 -SPS, 315 to 405 nm), excited nitrogen cation (N_2^+ -FNS, 390 to 440 nm) and $\cdot\text{OH}$ emission at 309 nm [33] along with weak $\cdot\text{O}$ emissions (777 and 844 nm) [34], and O_2^+ (427 nm) [35]. Under argon-plasma, the spectrum for both reactors is dominated by multiple argon transition lines (696 to 852 nm), $\cdot\text{OH}$ and weak $\cdot\text{O}$ emissions; a detailed allocation of each transition line to a specific species can be found in Rezaei et al. (2018) [36]. It is important to note that current OES provide only qualitative information about the plasma species generated in the gas phase (arbitrary units) with the purpose to be correlated with the secondary species generated inside the aqueous phase (see discussion below on the comparison of plasma species formation in water between air- and argon-plasma). The different OES spectra between air and argon result in the generation of different species within the aqueous solution, as shown in the next section.

3.2.2 *Quantification of plasma species in the liquid phase and physicochemical water properties*

Recently, the contribution of major short-lived and long-lived plasma species to the degradation of persistent and difficult-to-degrade PFASs has been revealed. Long-lived reactive nitrogen species (RNS), such as NO_3^- and NO_2^- , and reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as H_2O_2 , have been found to indirectly affect PFOA removal through the generation of ONOOH , $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ and $\cdot\text{OH}$ (see reactions R1-R5 in section 3.3) [37]. In particular, ONOOH and $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ directly affect PFOA degradation, while $\cdot\text{OH}$, even if not very effective for the direct degradation of PFOA, plays an important role in the chain reactions leading to PFOA defluorination [37, 38].

Therefore, it was essential to investigate the aforementioned species of interest (NO_3^- , NO_2^- , $\cdot\text{OH}$, H_2O_2 , O_3) under different reactor configurations, water matrices and plasma gases, used in this study. In the meanwhile, both pH and conductivity were monitored over the treatment time, as they are important influencing factors for the generation of the desired species in a plasma system [17], but also directly influence plasma discharge area and the interfacial concentration of surfactant-like contaminants, such as PFOA.

In Fig. 3a, a comparison of the aforementioned plasma species between gas-liquid DBD and DBD-based underwater plasma microbubbles is provided. Different plasma-liquid interactions between the two plasma reactors resulted in much higher concentrations of long-lived species (H_2O_2 , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , O_3) within gas-liquid DBD compared to underwater plasma bubbles under air atmosphere. In particular, the concentration of H_2O_2 increased as a function of time for both reactors with its value being ~150 times higher for gas-liquid DBD after 20 min of treatment (414 mg/L compared to 2.7 mg/L in underwater plasma bubbles). Furthermore, a steady increase of NO_3^- concentration was observed in both reactors, bring 1660 mg/L and 208 mg/L for gas-liquid DBD and

plasma bubbles, respectively after 20 min of air-plasma treatment. So, it turns out, that NO_3^- concentration was ~8 times higher in gas-liquid DBD compared to plasma bubbles. Nitrite concentration was negligible in plasma bubble reactor, while for the gas-liquid DBD increased up to 3.6 mg/L after 2 min of treatment and then decayed into zero for prolonged treatment times. The difference in nitrite and nitrate formation between the two air-plasma systems is consistent with the pH of the treated solution (Fig. 3d). For gas-liquid DBD, the pH decreased from 6.2 to 1.3 after 20 min of treatment, while for plasma bubbles it reduced to 2.9 due to lower $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ concentration. Therefore, a continuous increase in conductivity with treatment time (Fig. S2) was implied for both plasma systems, which was equal to 5460 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 950 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for gas-liquid DBD and plasma bubbles respectively, at the end of the treatment. Ozone concentration was also an increasing function of treatment time in both reactors, but once again the gas-liquid DBD treatment resulted in enhanced species concentration compared to the plasma bubbles treatment. After 20 min of treatment, O_3 concentration was ~8 times higher for gas-liquid DBD compared to plasma bubbles (i.e. 14.5 and 1.8 mg/L, respectively).

The main reasons for the different plasma species concentrations and water physicochemical properties between gas-liquid DBD and underwater plasma microbubbles have been previously discussed [30]. Briefly, the direct and intense contact between plasma and water in the gas-liquid DBD reactor promotes physicochemical reactions resulting in high concentrations of long-lived plasma species (Fig. 3a), a drastic decrease in solution pH (Fig. 3d) and a significant increase in solution conductivity (Fig. S2). In contrast, the DBD produced in the center of the plasma bubble reactor (between the two quartz tubes, Fig. S1) pre-activates the plasma gas that comes in contact with the aqueous phase through the underwater bubble,

resulting in much lower long-lived species concentrations and less pronounced changes in pH and conductivity. This is a consequence of the reduced electric field strength inside the underwater plasma bubble compared to the DBD in the center of the plasma bubble reactor [29], resulting in a lower electron ionization rate and reduced electron energy inside the bubble. An additional reason is that the rapid bursting of bubbles does not allow extensive transformation of short-lived species into long-lived ones through recombination reactions unlike gas-liquid DBD.

In contrast to long-lived species, the concentration of short-lived $\cdot\text{OH}$ was found to be higher in water treated with plasma bubbles compared to that treated with gas-liquid DBD [30]. In particular, the maximum $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration was 13.2 mg/L and 6.5 mg/L for plasma bubbles and gas-liquid DBD, respectively, and thus ~ 2 -fold higher production of short-lived species was realized under underwater plasma bubbles treatment. For both reactors, a decrease in $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration was observed at longer treatment times, possibly due to consumption of terephthalic acid used as a trapping reagent and excess H_2O_2 (especially for gas-liquid DBD).

The effect of water matrix on the formation of the various plasma species was also thoroughly investigated. Thus, the concentration of all the aforementioned RONS in ultrapure and tap water was measured along with the physicochemical properties of the air-liquid DBD treated water (Fig. 3b and d). Apparently, the concentration of O_3 , and NO_3^- was very similar in ultrapure and tap water, while the concentration of H_2O_2 was slightly lower in tap compared to ultrapure water. However, NO_2^- and $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration in tap water was higher compared to that in ultrapure water. The higher $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration is likely due to the less acidification effect of the plasma treatment in tap water (nearly neutral initial pH of tap water) which also likely led to an enhanced decomposition of ozone to $\cdot\text{OH}$ [39]. In particular, the pH of ultrapure water decreased

significantly from 6.2 to 1.3, while the initial pH of tap water was 6.8 and, due to the buffering ability of carbonate compounds, decreased at a slower rate compared to ultrapure water (Fig. 3d). Consequently, the conductivity of ultrapure water increased from 5 to 5460 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, while that of tap water from 507 to 4470 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Fig. S2). The lower increase of conductivity in the case of tap water could be related to the hydronium anions produced upon acid dissociation, which in turn are neutralized by carbonate compounds to form H_2CO_3 . In contrast, in ultrapure water where carbonates are absent, the hydronium anions remain in the liquid and thus contribute to a greater increase in conductivity compared to tap water [40].

Finally, a comparison on plasma species formation between air- and argon-plasma was conducted (Fig. 3c). Comparison was made for tap water and gas-liquid DBD treatment where more effective PFOA degradation was achieved (see results below). The concentrations of $\cdot\text{OH}$, O_3 and H_2O_2 were slightly higher under argon-plasma compared to air-plasma. At the end of treatment, the concentration of $\cdot\text{OH}$, O_3 and H_2O_2 under argon-plasma were 4.7, 32 and 260 mg/L, respectively, while the corresponding ones under air-plasma were 1.8, 17 and 173 mg/L. Moreover, under argon-plasma, no NO_x is produced in the gas phase of the plasma and thus, reasonably, a negligible concentration of NO_2^- and NO_3^- was detected in the plasma-treated water. Consequently, the pH of the solution did not decrease, but increased from 6.8 to 8.7 in contrast to that under air-plasma which decreased to 1.9 at the end of the treatment (Fig. 3d). Correspondingly, the conductivity increased from 507 to 4470 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ under air-plasma and decreased to 384 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ under argon-plasma, after 20 min of treatment (Fig. S2). The increased pH in tap water during plasma treatment, under argon atmosphere, can be attributed to the presence of chloride in the tap water and the excess of OH^- in the solution through electrolytic reactions associated with the chlor-alkali process [40].

Figure 3. Comparison of H_2O_2 , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , O_3 , and $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration in plasma-treated water between: (a) gas-liquid DBD and underwater plasma microbubbles (PMB) reactor (water matrix: ultrapure water (UPW); plasma gas: air); (b) ultrapure and tap water (plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD; plasma gas: air); (c) air- and argon-plasma (plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD; water matrix: tap water) and (d) solution pH during gas-liquid DBD and PMB treatment for different water matrices (ultrapure or tap water) and plasma gases (air or argon). Fixed parameter in all experiments: HV waveform: micropulses.

3.3 Comparison between air-liquid DBD and DBD-based underwater air-plasma bubbles on PFOA degradation efficiency and energy yield

Previous studies reported enhanced PFAS degradation in water when microbubbles were introduced into the plasma discharge, mainly due to the enhancement of the gas-liquid interface (see for instance [41]). In these studies, plasma discharge is generated above the water surface (gas-liquid treatment) and gas bubbles (not plasma bubbles) are introduced inside the water, enhancing the degradation of PFAS. Furthermore, as already mentioned in the Introduction, a growing number of publications [29, 30], report enhanced degradation of several classes of pollutants other than PFAS (e.g. dyes and antibiotics) by underwater air-plasma bubbles compared to air-liquid plasma treatment, mainly due to enhanced mass transport of plasma species from the gas to the liquid phase.

The aim of the present study was to compare gas-liquid plasma treatment with underwater plasma bubble treatment for PFOA degradation in water and not to confirm the positive effect of introducing microbubbles into the aqueous phase during gas-liquid DBD treatment. The comparison between the two DBD plasma reactor configurations

revealed the superiority of air-liquid plasma over underwater air-plasma microbubbles towards the degradation of PFOA in water. In particular, almost complete degradation of PFOA (~99%) was achieved after 20 min of air-liquid DBD treatment whereas underwater air-plasma bubbles were less effective recording a PFOA degradation of 40.8% after 30 min of treatment (Fig. 4a). The energy yield of air-liquid DBD treatment ranged from 1.63 to 0.5 mg/kWh (corresponding to PFOA degradation in the range 54.4% - 99.9%) while that of underwater air-plasma bubbles ranged from 3.85 to 1.55 mg/kWh but for much lower PFOA degradation (in the range of 16.9% to 40.8%) (Fig. 4b). In other words, for a similar energy yield (~1.6 mg/kWh), PFOA degradation was 40.8% and 54.4% for underwater air-plasma bubbles and air-liquid DBD, respectively. Thus, in order to completely destruct PFOA, air-liquid DBD constitutes a more appealing solution compared to underwater air-plasma bubbles.

From all the above, it becomes evident that DBD-based air-plasma bubbles are less effective to degrade PFOA in water compared to air-liquid DBD treatment. This is directly related to the surfactant-like character of PFAS having the tendency to exist in the water surface. In other words, the superiority of air-liquid DBD treatment is due to the close proximity of the plasma reactive species (produced near this interface) to the PFOA monomers present on the liquid surface. Next steps may include an extensive comparison between gas-liquid DBD and plasma bubbles under non-air plasma gases (e.g. argon) for short- and long-chain PFAS.

An additional reason for the superiority of air-liquid DBD treatment may be related to the different concentrations of plasma species and the different physicochemical properties of the plasma treated water compared to those in the underwater plasma microbubbles reactor (Fig. 3a and d). The much higher nitrate, nitrite and hydrogen peroxide concentrations measured during air-liquid DBD treatment compared to those

from air-plasma bubble treatment (Fig. 3a) may result in increased production of other short-lived RNS, such as ONOOH and $\cdot\text{NO}_2$, which have been found to be key-contributors to PFOA degradation [37]. For instance, UV light emitted by plasma can convert NO_3^- to ONOOH (R1), $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ and $\cdot\text{OH}$ (R2), while NO_2^- can react with $\cdot\text{OH}$ to produce $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ (R3) [42]. Furthermore, under acidic conditions, ONOOH can be produced through the reaction of H_2O_2 and NO_2^- (R4), but can also be decomposed to $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ and $\cdot\text{OH}$ (R5):

Furthermore, another reason that may promote PFOA degradation during air-liquid DBD treatment may be related to the increased conductivity of the plasma-treated water (Fig. S2), since conductivity directly affects the plasma discharge area and the interfacial concentration of surfactant-like contaminants [37].

It is noteworthy that the higher pH of plasma-treated water derived from underwater air-plasma bubbles compared to that of air-liquid DBD (Fig. 3d), was not sufficient to enhance the degradation of PFOA, although it has been reported that higher pH is preferable for PFAS degradation [43-45]. All of the above suggests that air-plasma degradation of PFOA is strongly influenced by its surfactant nature and RNS concentrations.

Figure 4. Comparison between underwater air-plasma microbubbles and air-liquid DBD for the (a) degradation of PFOA and (b) process energy yield (HV waveform: micropulses; initial PFOA concentration: 1 mg/L; water matrix: ultrapure water).

3.4 Effect of plasma gas on PFOA degradation in ultrapure water

As a means of process optimization, plasma chemistry certainly plays a defining role. In order to alter the nature of plasma species in the plasma-treated water, various plasma gases (air, oxygen, argon and nitrogen) were investigated for the degradation of PFOA in ultrapure water. The main reactions for the generation of plasma species under the different atmospheres of this study can be found in S4. Obviously, PFOA degradation was highly influenced by the nature of plasma gas and the order of degradation performance was as follows: air > nitrogen > argon > oxygen (Fig. 5a). The corresponding pseudo-first-order apparent rate constants of PFOA degradation were 0.20, 0.14, 0.10 and 0.03 min⁻¹, for air, nitrogen, argon and oxygen, respectively (Fig. 5b). For instance, after 15 min of gas-liquid DBD treatment, PFOA was degraded by ~91%, ~84%, ~76% and ~37% under air, nitrogen argon and oxygen-plasma, respectively. It is noteworthy that after 30 min of treatment, PFOA was completely

degraded (>99.9%) by air-plasma, while a remarkable PFOA degradation was achieved under nitrogen- and argon-plasma which were 98.8% and 95.1%, respectively. In contrast, a lower degradation of PFOA (~63%) was achieved under oxygen-plasma even after 30 min of treatment.

The outstanding PFOA degradation under air- and nitrogen-plasma is indicative of the significant contribution of some RNS, generated exclusively under nitrogen-containing gases. As already mentioned above, short-lived RNS, such as ONOOH and $\cdot\text{NO}_2$, have been found to be key-contributors to PFOA degradation [37]. Furthermore, the accumulation of nitrate and nitrite in solution can give a further source of hydroxyl radical because their UV photolysis is a well-known process able to produce hydroxyl radical in solution (e.g. reaction R2 in section 3.3). Therefore, the synergistic action of RNS with plasma electrons, hydrated electrons e_{aq}^- and other ROS (e.g. $\cdot\text{OH}$) also produced under air- and nitrogen-plasma [17, 46] result in almost complete degradation of PFOA. It is worth noting that this very high degradation of PFOA under air and nitrogen is achieved despite the acidification of the treated solution during the treatment (see results in section 3.2) which has been found to negatively affect its degradation [43].

In addition to RONS, the very high PFOA degradation under argon-plasma highlights that hydrated electrons, free plasma electrons and argon ions, which are intensely produced under argon atmosphere, are among the major species involved in its degradation [38, 47]. The attack of plasma electrons, aqueous electrons, and argon ions on the $-\text{COOH}$ functional group of the PFOA molecule has been found to generate unstable perfluoroalkyl species which in turn may lead to plethora of degradation reactions where $\cdot\text{OH}$ is also involved [40, 48].

On the other hand, the lower efficiency of oxygen-plasma compared to the other plasma gases (Fig. 5), indicates that the role of certain ROS (e.g. H_2O_2 , $^1\text{O}_2$, O_3 , $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) in the degradation of PFOA is limited, but not negligible in agreement with previous studies on PFAS destruction by plasma [49]. Indeed, many studies have confirmed that $\cdot\text{OH}$ play major role on the removal of PFOA but cannot initiate decomposition reactions [50]. Specifically, $\cdot\text{OH}$ can react with $\text{C}_7\text{F}_{15}\cdot$ to form $\text{C}_7\text{F}_{15}\text{OH}$ which is further oxidized by $\cdot\text{OH}$. Furthermore, it has been reported that singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), and superoxide anion radicals ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) cannot initiate the PFOA degradation process [51]. This is in contrast to many plasma-related studies on the degradation of organic pollutants other than PFAS (e.g. antibiotics, dyes) where oxygen prevails over other plasmas due to the oxidizing action of ROS (e.g. O_3 , $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) [52]. However, the electronegativity of fluorine contributes to the unique properties of C-F bonds present in PFOA, including their strength (dissociation energy of 116 kcal/mol), stability, and resistance to cleavage by ROS. Therefore, techniques that could only provide oxygen oxidizing species are not very effective against PFAS destruction [53], while cleaving a C-F bond requires harsh conditions or highly specialized reagents, such as strong acids or strong reducing agents. In conclusion, the plasma reactive oxygen species that typically prevail on the destruction of other organic pollutants may also participate in the PFOA degradation but not as the key-role players.

Figure 5. (a) PFOA degradation efficiency at different plasma gases and (b) pseudo-first-order PFOA degradation kinetics at different plasma gases (HV waveform: micropulses; plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD; initial PFOA concentration: 1 mg/L; water matrix: ultrapure water).

3.5 Effect of water parameters on PFOA degradation efficiency

3.5.1 Initial concentration of PFOA

Besides air-liquid DBD treatment at initial PFOA concentration of 1 mg/L, experiments were also performed at 0.1 and 10 mg/L (Fig. 6). PFAS concentration in drinking water is in the range of the ng/L, however in industrial water/wastewater much higher concentrations of PFAS are required to be treated [54]. Therefore, the effectiveness of the present approach in different PFOA concentrations was considered. When initial PFOA concentrations of 0.1, 1 and 10 mg/L were treated by air-liquid DBD, a sufficient PFOA degradation was achieved even at 10 min of treatment, which was ~73% (10 mg/L) and ~83% (0.1 and 1 mg/L). By extending the treatment time to 15 min, the degradation reached 90% for the three different initial PFOA concentrations. It was

almost completely degraded (i.e. 99%) after 20 min of plasma treatment. Similarly, based on the apparent rate constants (inset of Fig. 6), the degradation rate of 0.1 and 1 mg/L was similar ($\sim 0.16 \text{ min}^{-1}$), while for 10 mg/L was slightly lower (0.15 min^{-1}), indicating the slower PFOA degradation compared to 0.1 and 1 mg/L. It is evident that air-liquid DBD treatment is highly effective for PFOA degradation in the whole range of 10 to 0.1 mg/L at short treatment times.

Figure 6. PFOA degradation efficiency for different pollutant initial concentrations in water (HV waveform: micropulses; plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD; plasma gas: air; water matrix: ultrapure water).

3.5.2. Effect of water matrix under air and argon atmospheres

Because water matrix imposes different physicochemical properties of the water, it has been found to significantly affect the organic pollutant destruction by plasma processes. To investigate the difference of PFOA degradation under different water matrix, 0.1 and 1.0 mg/L of PFOA solution were prepared in ultrapure and tap water and treated with air-liquid DBD (Fig. 7). No significant alterations were observed between the two

water matrices in agreement with the similar plasma species concentrations and physicochemical water properties presented in Fig. 2. For an initial PFOA concentration of 0.1 mg/L, PFOA degradation was not affected by the water matrix (Fig. 7a). For higher initial concentration (1 mg/L), PFOA degradation in ultrapure water was slightly higher (~10%) compared to that in tap water for short plasma treatment times, while it was almost completely degraded (>99%) after 20 min of treatment for both water matrices (Fig. 7b).

The impact of water matrix on PFOA degradation becomes pronounced when argon is used for plasma generation, since PFOA was degraded much faster in tap water compared to ultrapure water under argon-plasma (Fig. 7c) in agreement with very recent findings [55]. Specifically, after 10 min of argon-liquid DBD treatment, the PFOA degradation efficiency in tap water was ~93%, much higher compared to ~58% degradation in ultrapure water. Furthermore, the PFOA degradation efficiency in tap water was 99% and 99.9% after 15 and 20 min of treatment, respectively with the corresponding efficiencies being ~76% and ~90% in ultrapure water. Similarly, the corresponding pseudo-first-order apparent rate constant of PFOA degradation was 0.31 and 0.10 min⁻¹ for tap and ultrapure water, respectively (Fig. 7d).

The most PFOA degradation efficiency was archived when argon used as plasma gas and tap water employed as water matrix. The reason could be the different physicochemical properties of the argon-plasma activated tap water (results presented in section 3.2). In particular, the alkaline conditions prevailing during PFOA treatment (i.e. pH ~9) result in a negligible concentration of hydronium anions that have been found to scavenge hydrated electrons (reaction 1) which are among the key species for PFOA degradation. In other words, the lower pH of air-plasma activated water

(ultrapure and tap) and argon-plasma activated ultrapure water results in the loss of hydrated electrons through reaction with hydronium ions [55]:

The critical role of solution pH in PFOA degradation and its enhancement at pH >7 has also been reported in γ -irradiation experiments in PFOA-contaminated water [56].

However, the almost complete degradation of PFOA (>99%) in both water matrices under air-liquid DBD despite unfavorable acidic conditions, highlights the important contribution of some RNS, as already discussed in section 3.3. In conclusion, the results on the effect of the water matrix on the degradation of PFOA confirm the potential of cold plasma to destroy PFOA since its degradation was similar (air-plasma) or enhanced (argon-plasma) in a more realistic water matrix.

Figure 7. Comparison of PFOA degradation between ultrapure (UP) and tap water under (a) air-plasma and initial PFOA concentration 0.1 mg/L, (b) air-plasma and initial PFOA concentration 1 mg/L, (c) argon-plasma and initial PFOA concentration 1 mg/L and (d) pseudo-first-order PFOA degradation kinetics under argon-plasma (HV waveform: micropulses; plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD).

3.6 Comparison of PFOA degradation between HV micro- and nanosecond pulses

3.6.1 Degradation efficiency by air-liquid and argon-liquid DBD

The HV waveform used to energize the reactor and produce the plasma has been found to substantially affect the energy efficiency of the process [17, 57]. Nanopulsed-plasma has been found to be very cost-effective for the destruction of various classes of contaminants (e.g. dyes, antibiotics) [58-60]. Therefore, it was investigated whether the use of HV nanopulses can achieve the recently set goal of more energy-efficient destruction of PFAS by plasma [31]. In particular, the degradation of PFOA in tap water was examined in the gas-liquid DBD reactor energized by HV nanopulses under both air and argon gas and compared with the results obtained by HV micropulses.

The comparison between HV nanosecond pulses (nsp) and microsecond pulses (μ sp) in terms of PFOA degradation kinetics is shown in Fig. 8. Superior performance of the micropulsed gas-liquid DBD compared to the nanopulsed system was observed in both air and argon atmospheres (Fig.8). In particular, after 10 min of treatment a very high PFOA degradation was achieved for the micropulsed-argon treatment (~93%), followed by micropulsed-air (~73%), nanopulsed-argon (~67%) and nanopulsed-air (~39%). For complete PFOA degradation (>99.9%), 20 min of treatment by micropulsed-argon was required, followed by micropulsed-air (30 min) and nanopulsed-argon (60 min), while nanopulsed-air was not able to completely degrade PFOA after 60 min of treatment with the maximum degradation efficiency being ~76% (Fig. 8a). The corresponding pseudo-first order apparent rate constants of PFOA degradation were 0.31, 0.17, 0.09 and 0.03 min^{-1} for micropulsed-argon, micropulsed-air, nanopulsed-argon and nanopulsed-air, respectively (Fig. 8b).

Furthermore, the higher performance of argon-plasma compared to air-plasma for PFOA degradation in tap water is due to reasons related to water physicochemical

properties and species formation, as already discussed. It is reminded here that the comparison between HV waveforms was performed for PFOA destruction in tap water to be close to real-life conditions, reiterating cold plasma as a promising method for PFAS destruction that should be further investigated. In conclusion, microsecond pulses prevail over nanosecond ones in terms of PFOA degradation kinetics, but this is related to the much higher energy plasma supplied in the DBD which was ~ 50 times higher when the reactor was energized by HV microsecond pulses (Table 1) leading to much higher plasma species concentration compared to HV nanopulses. However, the DBD power should be considered for a fair comparison between the different HV waveforms towards PFOA destruction and therefore the following section is dedicated to comparing micropulses and nanopulses in terms of energy efficiency.

Figure 8. (a) Comparison between HV microsecond pulses (μ sp) and HV nanosecond pulses (nsp) for PFOA degradation in tap water under air- and argon-plasma and (b) first-order degradation kinetics of PFOA degradation (plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD; initial PFOA concentration: 1 mg/L).

3.6.2 Energy efficiency

Determining energy yield and electrical energy per order provides a clear indication of the overall performance of a treatment method in terms of cost-effectiveness. To that goal, the energy yield of PFOA degradation in tap water by gas-liquid DBD plasma was calculated and compared between the four different systems (i.e. micropulsed-argon, micropulsed-air, nanopulsed-argon and nanopulsed-air) (Fig. 9a). The energy yield decreased as PFOA degradation efficiency increased regardless of the applied HV waveform and plasma gas applied to the gas-liquid DBD reactor. Furthermore, HV nanopulses were superior to HV micropulses under both air and argon plasma gas, while the argon-plasma dominates the air-plasma regardless of the HV waveform applied to the reactor with the order being nanopulsed-argon > nanopulsed-air > micropulsed-argon > micropulsed-air. For almost complete PFOA destruction in tap water (>99%), the energy yield was ~19.0, ~1.5 and ~0.6 mg/kWh for nanopulsed-argon, micropulsed-argon and micropulsed-air, respectively.

Besides energy yield, the electrical energy per order E_{EO} (electrical energy) that is necessary to reduce the concentration of a contaminant by one order of magnitude in a unit volume of water [61], was also calculated. The E_{EO} was equal to ~23.6 kWh/m³, ~385 kWh/m³ and ~915 kWh/m³ for nanopulsed-argon, micropulsed-argon and micropulsed-air, respectively (Fig. 9b). The E_{EO} for the nanopulsed-air system was not calculated since the PFOA degradation not reached >90% within the treatment time of this study. Apparently, the E_{EO} of the present nanopulsed-driven gas-liquid DBD plasma reactor was ~16 times lower compared to the micropulsed-system under argon-plasma and lower compared to existing efforts for PFOA degradation [25, 31, 49, 62]. It is important to note that very low energy consumption could be achieved by following the foam fractionation method. However, PFOA contamination is transferred to the

foam as no PFOA degradation occurs, which is a strong limitation of foam fractionation (Table 2). In addition, other degradation processes such as photocatalysis, microwave decomposition with persulfate, and ultrasonic degradation require higher energy consumption compared to the present nanopulsed gas-liquid DBD plasma, while some of them (e.g. photocatalysis) produce secondary pollution.

The quite low E_{EO} achieved for PFOA destruction in tap water in the nanopulsed gas-liquid DBD is due to the enormously high instantaneous power (~ 1300 kW) of nanosecond duration (Fig. 2b) directed to the plasma reactor resulting in high mean electron energies and generation of remarkable concentration of plasma species even at very low mean DBD power (Table 1) thus increasing the production yield of plasma species (concentration of plasma species per energy consumed).

The main challenge of this highly energy-efficient and effective process is to prove its effectiveness on a larger scale. Considering that lab-scale optimization studies are needed before scaling-up the system, the results of the present study could form the basis for the construction of plasma reactors on a larger scale. In particular, based on the design of the current lab-scale reactors, gas-liquid DBD and plasma microbubbles reactors able to treat much larger water volumes can be constructed and tested. For pilot-scale application, the next steps may include the design and construction of plasma reactors consisting of multiple DBD electrode systems (gas-liquid or plasma bubbles), while for the treatment of even larger water volumes, the parallel operation of the aforementioned pilot-scale reactors will be required.

Figure 9. Comparison between HV microsecond pulses (μsp) and HV nanosecond pulses (nsp) for PFOA degradation in tap water under air and argon atmospheres in terms of (a) energy yield and (b) electrical energy per order (plasma reactor: gas-liquid DBD; initial PFOA concentration: 1 mg/L).

Table 2. Comparison of different methods applied for the degradation/removal of PFOA from water.

Method	Operating Conditions	Advantages/Disadvantages	E_{EO} (kWh/m ³)	Ref
Foam fractionation alone or combined with other method	540 min, groundwater leachate	Low cost/Secondary pollution	~0.1-76	[63, 64]
Electrochemical oxidation	180 min, 100 mg/L	Effective/High treatment times, Difficult scale-up	~144	[65, 66]
Photocatalysis	420 min, 60 mg/L	Low-cost/High treatment times, secondary pollution	~1458	[67]
Ultrasonic degradation	90 min, 1 mg/L	Easy to implement/High cost	~500-5000	[68]
Sonolysis	60 min, 10 mg/L	Easy to implement/High cost	~4045	[69]
Microwave–hydrothermal treatment with persulfate	60 min, 100 mg/L	Effective/High cost	~2599	[70]

Plasma degradation		Effective, green, low-cost/ Scale-up is challenging		
Needle-plate pulsed discharge integrated with microbubbles	Argon, 120 min, 30 mg/L		216.5	[41]
Nanopulsed dual jet plasma	Air, 60 min, groundwater ppt levels		~45	[62]
Reverse vortex flow gliding arc plasma	Air, 60 min, recycle rate of 20 mL/min. ~100 mg/L, 50 L/min gas flow		~213.4	[49]
Nanopulsed gas-liquid DBD plasma	Argon, 30 min, 1 mg/L		~23.6	This study

4. Conclusions

A comparative investigation of different DBD plasma reactor configurations, pulsed-plasma waveforms, water matrices and plasma gases for the degradation of PFOA and the composition of plasma-treated water was carried out. The surfactant nature of PFOA, as well as the higher RNS concentrations and conductivity of the plasma-treated water, resulted in enhanced PFOA degradation within the air-liquid DBD (~99% PFOA degradation after 20 min of treatment) compared to the air-plasma bubbles (~41% PFOA degradation after 30 min of treatment). In ultrapure water, PFOA was degraded very efficiently by air, nitrogen and argon plasma (air > nitrogen > argon), whereas oxygen plasma was less efficient, indicating that RNS, argon ions, plasma electrons and hydrated electrons contribute significantly to PFOA degradation in contrast to the limited involvement of ROS. The degradation of PFOA was very efficient (>99.9% after 30 min of treatment) over the whole range of its initial concentration in water (0.1 to 10 mg/L). Furthermore, PFOA degradation was similar (air-plasma) or enhanced (argon-plasma) in tap water compared to ultrapure water. In tap water, the highest degradation of PFOA was achieved under argon-plasma (>99.9% PFOA degradation after 20 min of treatment) possibly due to the prevailing alkaline conditions (pH ~8.7) that resulted in the enhancement of hydrated electrons in solution. Under HV

micropulses, the power dissipated in the plasma reactor was significantly higher compared to that under HV nanopulses (~50-fold) resulting in faster PFOA degradation. However, the much lower energy requirements of nanopulsed-plasma resulted in increased production yield of plasma species and reduced electrical energy per order (E_{EO}). The E_{EO} of PFOA degradation in tap water by gas-liquid DBD was 16 times lower for nanopulsed-argon (~23.6 kWh/m³) compared to micropulsed-argon (~385 kWh/m³) and one of the lowest compared to other methods. This study provides important information on the appropriate plasma reactor geometry, plasma energy source and conditions that optimize the treatment of PFOA-contaminated water.

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